

University of Southampton GEM MSc Semester 1
School of Geography, 2009/10
Student: Lemenkova Polina
ID: 3 23369248
GEOG6062 Core Skills in Remote Sensing

Essay

Landsat Imagery and ENVI Techniques for Investigating of Bracken Spread in the New Forest National Park (UK, Hampshire).

Introduction

During the last 10 years the environmental conditions in the New Forest (Hampshire, UK) has changed dramatically: the natural ecosystem structure of this unique natural reserve has been affected by the invasion of the bracken (*Pteridium aquilinum*) – the noxious weed that has spread rapidly over the area of 10*10 km in the New Forest (Fig.1).

Fig.1. Photo of bracken (*Pteridium aquilinum*) (Taken from http://www.ubcbotanicalgarden.org/potd/2007/11/pteridium_aquilinum.php)

This paper focuses on remote sensing techniques advantages for environmental monitoring and investigating the endangered area using ENVI software and Landsat Imagery. Using satellite imagery classification will highlight the exact area where the spread of bracken has taken place, its change during the years, and the speed of bracken's spreading year by year (change of bracken

coverage in percents), thus helping in environmental decisions making and protecting the unique ecosystem of the National Park of the New Forest.

Type of the imagery chosen

For the vegetation monitoring we used imagery for detection vegetation damages and environmental changes. The **Landsat TM** is probably most suitable to choose for this purpose due to the following reason: it has the resolution types most suitable for the vegetation classification: spatial, temporal, spectral and radiometric resolution (Table 1, comparing with MSS). Comparing with other types of satellites sensors (like geostationary satellites) it has more sharp spatial resolution. If compare with SPOT, the last one has much higher altitude of orbit 832 km (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000) than Landsat with 705 km (Lillesand) which enables to the

Fig.2 **Landsat 7** imagery, taken from: <http://www.satimagingcorp.com/satellite->

Landsat to have wider FOV and better spatial resolution.

With 30 meters Landsat's spatial resolution (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000) it is possible to distinguish clearly separate parts of the forest, which have nuances in their colour. That is helpful for identifying the areas of certain grass or trees, and is, therefore, perfect for forest ecosystem change detection. Temporal coverage of 16-day repeat cycle (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000) is the same for both MSS and TM and is representative enough to show the difference in bracken spread area throughout the period of interest (10 years). If compare with the temporal resolution of SPOT, the last has again lesser one than that of Landsat: 26 days (Lillesand)

The spectral resolution of Landsat includes both visible and IR spectral bands, so that we can make an NDVI classification which is the key instrument in our research. Comparing the radiometric resolution of Landsat TM with MSS, it is also clear that the characteristics and technical parameters of TM are better (8 bites) than by the Landsat MSS (7 bites). Taking into account all these technical characteristics of Landsat TM, and its comparison with other types of imagery, we suggest that **Landsat TM** is definitely suitable one for our research.

Table 1. Characteristics of the Landsat imaging devices (TM versus MSS)

(taken from Richards J., Xiuping J., p.13,).

Instrument	Spectral bands	IFOV	Dynamic Range (bt)
MSS	4. 0.5-0.6 (green)	79 * 79	7
	5 0.6 -0.7 (red)	79 * 79	7
	6 0.7 -0.8 (near IR)	79 * 79	7
	7 0.8 -1.1 (near IR)	79 * 79	6
	8 10.4–12.6 (thermal)	237 * 237	
TM	1 0.45 – 0.52 (blue)	30 * 30	8
	2 0.52-0.60 (green)	30 * 30	8
	3 0.63- 0.69 (red)	30 * 30	8
	4 0.76- 0.90 (near IR)	30 * 30	8
	5 1.55-1.75 (mid IR)	30 * 30	8
	6 2.08–2.35 (mid IR)	30 * 30	8
	7 10.4–12.5 (thermal)	120 * 120	8

It would be also helpful to have two image sets for 2009 and 1999 retrospectively.

Analysis Method

To analyze how dramatically the changes in the plant types of the New Forest were, we need to classify the Landsat satellite images using ENVI software. For the research we need at least two different images for separate data (e.g. 1999 and 2009 years), or better 10 different Landsat images from the 1999 until the 2009 with repeatability of one year. The images must be taken at the same month and time of day, best representative for vegetation structure: maximum green content of leaves is observed on the images the best over the months from May through September (Huete A. et al, 2002); we can take the month of July for our research. The images must be also taken from the

same sensor - Landsat TM, to avoid any geometric inaccuracies at different sensors and to provide the same viewing geometry, spectral bands, radiometric resolution of the images.

Fig. 3. National Part of New Forest, UK. Image taken from www.wikimapia.org

The key scheme for the research would include following procedures.

1. First of all, the satellite images must be geometrically corrected in the same way, so that we could compare them identically to avoid any geometrical errors (Richards and Xiuping, 1999). For that purpose we use large-scale topographic New Forest maps of 1:100.000 scale (or 1:200.000 as the smallest). The map must be scanned in a good resolution (300 dpi) and must be geo-referenced (GIS-registered) in the GIS itself. Alternatively, we may use following ground-truth data:
 - ✓ already GIS-registered another image
 - ✓ vector topographic map in GIS (with all necessary layers)
 - ✓ GPS data
2. Secondly, we need to enhance images by stressing the vegetation areas and making the nuances of green colours (Fig.4) of different vegetation types more distinguishable. For that purpose we use multi-image manipulation ratio techniques - EVI and NDVI, which allow us to receive more distinguishable and contrast-enhanced image of vegetation types in New Forest. NDVI index, though being previously calculated from AVHRR data, can also be used successfully while doing research based upon Landsat imagery (Oguro et al., 2001).

NDVI is a ratio of difference and sum of the values in spectral reflectance in NIR and red bands: $NDVI = (NIR - Red) / (NIR + Red)$, whereas the EVI is a more complicated, vegetation-adjusted ratio $EVI = G * (NIR - Red) / (NIR + C1 * Red - C2 * Blue + L)$ with more correction towards brightness, aerosol resistance and surface reflectance (Harris A., Lecture 10). We may use both methods to compare the results, or to choose one of them (NDVI). According to M. Bunkey (Bunkey et al, 2008), NDVI has less sensitivity towards relief effect, though it is sensitive towards soil radiation or atmospheric effects (Lillesand T.M., Kiefer R.W., 2000). We have finally chosen NDVI for our research, because it is suitable for any studies where temporal comparison for a single area is necessary (Mather, 1999).

3. At the third step, we classify each image using supervised classification. Among the necessary training stages we digitize areas of different types of vegetation: bracken, coniferous trees, deciduous trees, bushes and grass. The results will be presented as the output stage showing different classes of the image (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000). The areas must be clearly representative and complete examples of areas of interest. Of course, it is also necessary to digitize non-vegetation regions (miscellaneous, roads, etc).

Alternatively, we can use unsupervised classification and compare the results. At the unsupervised classification the classification is being made automatically, without training data polygons, so that the possible errors in identifying the areas of bracken can be avoided. The classes that we receive as a result of unsupervised classification are based solely upon the natural groupings (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000) and user can correct the number of classes and merge or split them accordingly. However, unsupervised classification is more useful when analyst has no idea about the location of the areas, and in our case it is better to use supervised classification, because we have previous knowledge of where bracken areas are spread mostly, due to the botanical observations in the New Forest.

Fig.4. Surroundings of New Forest National Park: Beaulieu, UK.

Each type of vegetation has its own spectral reflectance, due to chlorophyll content and leaf structure, and therefore, a nuance of colour. Image taken from www.wikimapia.org

4. After having classified images of New Forest for each year, we can subtract the image-1 (dated 1999) from the image-10 (dated 2009) to calculate the difference between them, to see the environmental changes, using the subtracting images method in ENVI. If we have 10 different images we may also subtract consequently each image from the next one to see the gradual changes, if the detailed research is necessary. The subtraction will show us the changes in the vegetation structure that happened during the 10 years.
5. At last, we create thematic map using the previous calculation of vegetation. The map shows areas damaged and is a result of classification. At the map the first, undamaged situation in 1999, and the last one in 2009 will be shown as two different areas (one within the other) to show the dynamic of spreading.

Additionally, we can create 10 different maps from each image for each year. These maps

would be parts of the short dynamic “movie film” - a series of separate maps, just to show the dynamics of vegetation changes more impressively. It can be made using ArcGIS.

Accuracy

As it is justly said (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000), the classification is not complete until its accuracy is assessed. In other words, it is necessary to assess how precise our calculations are. The accuracy assessment will be made using error matrix in ENVI. According to Lillesand (Lillesand and Kiefer, 2000), we can calculate both producer's accuracy, to show how well set pixels are classified ($\text{Number of pixels correctly classified} / \text{Total number of classified pixels}$), and the user's accuracy, to see how many pixels are classified correctly ($\text{Number of pixels correctly classified} / \text{Number of pixels that were classified in that category}$). The more the result is near 100 (perfect, ideal classification), the better our calculations are. Besides, we can collect adequate ground truth data directly from the field measurements. The area of 10*10 km can be re-measured by the land-surveyors group using GPS (3 persons will be enough: one botanist and two land-surveyors) to re-prove the actual borders of the bracken area.

Advantages, limitations

High temporal resolution of Landsat allows to find out images without clouds, so that we will have good chances to receive a high-quality images, which is, doubtlessly, one of the Landsat's advantages. Landsat Thematic Mapper images have been used a lot in different branches of resource management (forestry, geology, hydrology, etc), for mapping and environmental change detection (Johannsen and Sanders, 1982). Therefore, Landsat images are accurate and informative enough for detailed research of the Earth resources (Ustin, 2004).

One of the limitation in the change detection research using remote sensing can be the inaccuracies in classifications of separate images while making the training sites. Therefore, some areas of bracken can be interpreted as non-bracken which will lead to misinterpretation. It can entail inaccuracies in changes detection: some differences in areas may be too small (almost zero) while subtracting the images one from another.

Some limitation of the Landsat images may be their spatial resolution of 30 meters, which can lead to the fact that some separate areas of bracken that are less than 30 meters in diameter can be omitted from the classification

Conclusion

After applying different remote sensing procedures to the Landsat TM images (geometric correction, image enhancement, classification, images subtraction, and accuracy assessment), and making thematic maps, we have the clear and representative picture of how areas of the bracken weed progressed in the New Forest Natural Park during the past 10 years.

The result classified images can be merged with topographic maps and integrated into the GIS project. The final thematic maps, as well as classified images, can be part of the presentation paper for the environmental officers or other officials.

References:

1. Botany Photo of the Day: Pteridium aquilinum, [Online], November 8, 2007, Available: http://www.ubcbotanicalgarden.org/potd/2007/11/pteridium_aquilinum.php
2. Bunkei M., Wei Y., Jin C., Yuyichi O. and Guoyu Q., 2007, *Sensitivity of the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) to Topographic Effects: A Case Study in High-Density Cypress Forest*, [Online] Sensors, 7, 2636-2651 Available: <http://www.mdpi.org/sensors/papers/s7112636.pdf>
3. Harris A. Lectures 1-12, GEOG6062 Core Skills in Remote Sensing, 2009 [Online], Available: <https://blackboard.soton.ac.uk/>
4. Huete A., Didan K., Miura T., Rodriguez E. P., Gao X. and Ferreira L. G., 2002, [Online] Overview of the radiometric and biophysical performance of the MODIS vegetation indices. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/>
5. Imagery taken from www.wikimapia.org
6. Johannsen C. and Sanders J.L., 1982, *Remote sensing for resource Management*, Soil Conservation Society of America.
7. Lillesand T.M., Kiefer R.W., 2000, *Remote sensing and Image Interpretation*. 4th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York.
8. Mather P., 1999, *Computer processing of Remotely-Sensed Images*, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., Chichester.
9. Oguro Y., Imamoto C., Suga Y., S. Takeuchi, 2001. [Online], *Monitoring of Rice Field by Landsat-7 ETM+ and Landsat-5 TM Data*, 22nd Asian Conference of Remote Sensing. Available: <http://www.crisp.nus.edu.sg/~acrs2001/pdf/173OGURO.pdf>
10. Richards J., Xiuping J., 1999, *Remote Sensing Digital Image Analysis: An Introduction*, 3rd ed., Springer, Berlin.
11. Satellite Images Corporation internet-resources, <http://www.satimagingcorp.com/satellite-sensors/landsat.html>
12. Ustin S. L., 2004, *Remote Sensing for Natural Resources Management and Environmental Monitoring*, 3rd ed., Volume 4, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New Jersey.